

CATALAN MERSENNE NUMBERS AND DISCOVERY OF THE 53rd AND 54th KNOWN MERSENNE PRIMES

Cheong Siong Chua

September 12, 2025

Abstract

In this paper, we prove that all Catalan-Mersenne numbers are prime and hence present the 53rd and the 54th known Mersenne primes.

Keywords: Catalan Mersenne Numbers, Mersenne Primes

2020 Mathematics Subject Classification: Primary–11A41; Secondary–11A51

1 Introduction

Primes of the form $M_p = 2^p - 1$ are called Mersenne primes. There has been a long history [6] in the search of Mersenne primes. Catalan-Mersenne numbers is a sequence of numbers defined by $f(n) = 2^{f(n-1)} - 1$ with $f(0) = 2$. It is known that $f(0), f(1), f(2), f(3), f(4)$ are all primes. In this paper, we prove that all Catalan-Mersenne numbers are prime, hence presenting also the 53rd and 54th known Mersenne primes which are both more than a billion digits long.

2 Main Proof

Let

$$f(n+1) = 2^{f(n)} - 1$$

where $f(0) = 2$, we want to show that $f(n)$ is prime for all positive integers n .

Proof:

Let $\phi(n)$ be the Euler phi function.

Assume $f(n)$ is composite, it has distinct prime factors $p, p_2, \dots, p_j, j \geq 2$.

Let g be a primitive root mod p where p is the smallest prime factor of $f(n)$ and $g^k \equiv 2 \pmod{p}$, where k, c, d, e, h and m are integers. By Euler's theorem, $g^{\phi(f(n))} \equiv 1 \equiv g^{kf(n-1)} \pmod{p}$.

So, $\phi(f(n)) \equiv kf(n-1) \pmod{\phi(p)}$, thus $k = \frac{d\phi(p)}{f(n-1)}$ and $g^{kf(n-1)} \equiv 1 \pmod{g^{\phi(p)} - 1}$.

Since $g^{\phi(p)} - 1 = cp$, $g^{kf(n-1)} - 1 = f(n) = hcp$. So for some $j \geq 2$,

$$c = \frac{f(n)}{ph} = \frac{p^{\alpha_1-1} p_2^{\beta_2} \dots p_j^{\gamma_j}}{h} = mp_j$$

Note that $h \neq p^e p_2^{\beta_2} \dots p_j^{\gamma_j}$ for all integers e . Suppose it is, then $c = p^b$ for some integer b . This means $g^{\phi(p)} - p^{b+1} = 1$. But by Mihalescu's theorem, this cannot exist for $b \geq 1$ and for $b = 0$, $g^{\phi(p)} - p > 1$, so equality does not exist. So, $g^{\phi(p)} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}$.

Let $g^a = g_j$ be a primitive root mod p_j , so for some integer a , $g^{a\phi(p)} \equiv g_j^{\phi(p)} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}$ and $g_j^{\phi(p_j)} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j}$, where $\phi(p_j)$ is the order of $g_j \pmod{p_j}$. So $\phi(p_j) \leq \phi(p)$.

But p is the smallest prime factor of $f(n)$. This is a contradiction.

Thus $f(n)$ is prime for all positive integers n .

Hence, the proof of all Catalan-Mersenne numbers are primes is complete.

3 Results

As a consequence, we have the 53rd known Mersenne prime $f(5) = 2^{170141183460469231731687303715884105727} - 1$ with 51 217 599 719 369 681 875 006 054 625 051 616 350 digits long as well as the 54th known Mersenne prime $f(6) = 2^{2^{170141183460469231731687303715884105727} - 1} - 1$ with $\lfloor (2^{170141183460469231731687303715884105727} - 1) (\log_{10} 2) \rfloor + 1$ digits long. We have also thus shown that there is an infinite number of Mersenne primes.

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Cheong Siong Chua
Blk 691B Choa Chu Kang Crescent 12-60 Singapore 682691
Email: cheongsiong@yahoo.com
12 Sep 2025